

PREFERRED SOCIAL MEDIA NETWORKS AND ITS USAGE: A CASE STUDY ON ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Abstract

Social media services are web-based services which can be used by students via laptops, and mobile (Smartphone) & tablet computers. Using these services students can have highly interactive platform where they can also share images, videos, information's and even more with each other through a particular network. Currently social media plays a significant role in student's life in shopping, electronic mails, education and business tool etc. Social media acting as an imperative role in transforming student's life style. In recent days, the use of social networking sites has grown tremendously especially among the college students. This study investigates how college students are using social networks in their day to day life. Primary objective of the study is to know the way in which students use the various social media networks with the help of their Smartphone and to know the way they use. The study conducts survey among under graduate students of Government Arts and science colleges and measures the usage of their social media networks. The respondents of this study is the under graduate students studying in government colleges in cuddalore district of Tamilnadu. Questionnaire was designed to collect primary data from the respondents. The sample size of the research is limited to 100. The data were collected directly with the respondents, and the questionnaires were distributed directly to them. After collecting the primary data, its descriptive statistics are measured by using software SPSS 20.0 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for inference. The study results reveal that how often the respondents use the social medias such as WhatsApp, YouTube, and Face Book social medias.

Keywords: Social media, networking, Students, WhatsApp, YouTube, Facebook

Introduction

The recent statistics showed the most popular networks worldwide as of January 2020, and number of active accounts. Among the various networking sites Facebook was the first social network and plays as Market leader to surpass 1 billion registered accounts and currently sits at almost 2.45 billion monthly active users. Approximately 2 billion internet users are using social networks and these figures are still expected to grow as mobile device usage and mobile social networks increasingly gain traction. Students use social networks on a daily basis; they offer message and information services and get the chance to establish new relationships or maintain existing ones. Researchers indicate that the majority of teenagers spend at least 30 minutes daily on social media (Labrague 2014), so a significant part of their communication is performed through a social network and also new relationships are created. The use of social networking sites has changed the relationships and ways of communication among the students. The word "Social Media" represents collection of applications includes Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, LinkedIn, or YouTube etc. and websites that link students to share information. People from different age groups use social media; Social media plays an essential role in every body's life especially with students. Information Technology changed the living standard of people and these tools offer a number of ways of interaction and unusual opportunities to learn unfamiliar languages throughout wide-reaching. The social media transferred the world to global village, social media users can join with other people within short span of time and share ideas and give comments and people from different

nation or culture can also gossip on any matter. People also use social media to get information about other countries. Students use social media for learning purpose, for entertainment, and for innovation. Social Media in modern times has become the same with Social Networking sites. Social media can be defined as any web or mobile based platform that enables a person or agency to exchange a few words interactively and enables exchange of user generated content.

Review of Literature

Fodeman and Monroe (2009) studied the social network of Facebook. The authors gave eight reasons why students should not use websites and gives support for the claim. Some include time usage, false sense of privacy, scams targeting teens, the unawareness of how they are being marketed, lack of social interaction and unethical behaviors. (Subrahmanyam, Greenhold & Tyres 2004) stated that around the world more than eighty percent of our youths are spending a large amount of time on internet. The new age group of children and teenagers became the primary groups to utilize internet on a huge size. Social networking is an online interface service that manages to put together people and unite them with common interest (Boyd & Ellison, 2007). Some social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter, Google +, etc has paying attention to millions of user who have incorporated these sites into their daily practice. Naslund (2016) states that Social media refers to interactive web and mobile platforms through which individuals and communities share, co-create, or exchange information, ideas, photos, or videos within a virtual network. There are numerous social media sites users can choose from; today's generation has become so technology dependent. Students try to hunt for advice from the educational associated websites such as Google to provide their requirements from time to time. Social media is an intriguing new environment to study because technology is such an integral part of teenage life. Given its popularity, people have considerable concerns about the effects of social media on children, especially because adolescents may be more prone to risk-taking behavior that places their health at risk (Ahn, 2011).

Objectives of the study

- ✓ To understand the reason for using social networking sites among the students
- ✓ To understand how often the students spend on this social networking sites
- ✓ To know the students priority among various social networking sites

Scope of the study

In this study the researcher identified how social networking sites influence the students and it would able to give why students use smart phones. It also can identify which is the popular networking site among the students. The researcher conducted the study during December 2019 to February 2020, and the data were collected from the under graduate arts and science students from Cuddalore districts and the number of sample limited to 100, since the sample size is small the result of this study cannot be generalized.

Limitation of the study

This study limited to 100 Arts and science under graduate students who is studying in Government Arts and science colleges in Cuddalore district in Tamilnadu. The study results cannot be generalized as the number of sample is small. Another expected limitation in this study is that the youth might fail to give correct information on the basis of invasion of their privacy.

Material and Methodology:-

The study is based on survey method and under graduate students of Government Arts and Science colleges were chosen for the study as respondents. Age and sex were the demographic factors that taken for the study. This study consisted of 100 students studying in different Government Arts and Science colleges and data were collected based on simple random sampling. The primary objectives of the present study is to asses overall usage of social media on college students. Questionnaire was designed to collect primary data from the selected sample. The data were collected through direct conversation in which the questionnaires were distributed directly to the respondents and had face to face conversations and questioning them to know on the usage of Social networking sites. After collecting this primary data, its descriptive statistics are measured by using software SPSS 20.0 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for inference.

Analysis and Discussion

Table – 1 Profile of the Respondents

Factors		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	37	37.0	37.0
	Female	63	63.0	100.0
Family Type	Nuclear Family	12	12.0	12.0
	Joint Family	88	88.0	100.0
Marital Status	Married	14	14.0	14.0
	Unmarried	86	86.0	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table -1 shows the profile of the respondents of this study, among the respondents 37 percent of the respondents are male and 63 percent of the respondents are female. In the case of type of family the respondents belongs, 12 percent of them come from nuclear family and 88 percent of them belongs to joint family and among the respondents 14 percent of them are married and 86 percent of them are single.

Table -2 Brand preference of the Respondents

			Price	Offers	Features	Advertisement	Performance	Total
BRAND	Apple	Count	1	0	1	0	0	2
		% within BRAND	50.0%	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	
	Samsung	Count	6	4	8	0	8	25
		% within BRAND	24.0%	16.0%	32.0%	0.0%	32.0%	
	Sony	Count	3	2	4	0	2	5
		% within BRAND	60.0%	40.0%	80.0%	0.0%	40.0%	
	Honor	Count	2	0	1	0	3	6
		% within BRAND	33.3%	0.0%	16.7%	0.0%	50.0%	

	Oppo	Count	2	0	1	0	0	3
		% within BRAND	66.7%	0.0%	33.3%	0.0%	0.0%	
	Vivo	Count	5	4	5	4	6	13
		% within BRAND	38.5%	30.8%	38.5%	30.8%	46.2%	
	Mi/Redmi	Count	5	4	5	4	6	46
		% within BRAND	52.5%	40.8%	78.5%	64.8%	38.0%	
Total		Count	19	10	20	4	19	100

Source: Primary Data

Table – 2 shows the brand of Smartphone they prefer to buy, among the respondents 46 percent of them highly preferred to buy Mi/Redmi brand of Smartphone., and 25 percent of the respondents prefer to buy Samsung brand and they give least preference to Apple brand at 2 percent level.

Table – 3 Gender wise Smartphone usage Behaviour

			Phone Calls	Browsing	Email	Shopping	Travel Planner	Social Media	News	Music	Picture	Total
GENDE R	Ma le	Count	33	19	12	10	5	17	12	20	13	37
		% withi n GEN DER	89.2%	51.4%	32.4%	27.0%	13.5%	45.9%	32.4%	54.1%	35.1%	
		% of Total	33.0%	19.0%	12.0%	10.0%	5.0%	17.0%	12.0%	20.0%	13.0%	37.0%
	Fe male	Count	64	9	15	7	6	46	23	49	29	63
		% withi n GEN DER	101.6%	14.3%	23.8%	11.1%	9.5%	73.0%	36.5%	77.8%	46.0%	
		% of Total	64.0%	9.0%	15.0%	7.0%	6.0%	46.0%	23.0%	49.0%	29.0%	63.0%
Total		Count	97	28	27	17	11	63	35	69	42	100
		% of Total	97.0%	28.0%	27.0%	17.0%	11.0%	63.0%	35.0%	69.0%	42.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary Data

Table -3 shows the purpose of using the Smartphone among male and female respondents. Among the respondents 33 percent of the male respondents and 64 percent of the female respondents used their Smart phone for phone calling, 20 percent of Male respondents and 49 percent of the female respondents given importance to listen music from their Smartphone.

Among the respondents 46 percent of female respondents and 17 percent of the male respondents use their Smartphone for watching social media.

Table - 4 Respondents preference towards social media

Preference level of Social Media	Rank									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Google +	16	9	18	29	12	11	2	2	1	
Linkedin	4			2	2	14	23	23	18	14
Facebook	2	22	36	18	8	3	3	4	3	1
Twitter		3	9	8	19	20	23	5	6	7
YouTube	13	28	21	13	16	3	1	3	2	
Instagram	4	9	9	10	16	22	7	13	8	2
Flickr	1			4	14	8	17	29	20	7
Snapchat	6	3	1	13	7	12	15	16	18	9
WhatsApp	54	25	4	3	4	1	1	2	4	2
Quora	2	2	1		2	6	8	5	19	55

Source: Primary Data

Table – 4 shows the respondent’s preference level towards using the social media. The respondents were asked to rank the various social media according to their preference to use, WhatsApp social media is used by the maximum of the respondents i.e. 54 percent of the respondents use this social media and it ranked first, and 28 percent of the respondents used YouTube social media and ranked second among the various social media sites. Face Book social media used by 36 percent of the respondents and ranked third and followed by other social media such as Google+ ranked fourth with 29 percent, Twitter ranked fifth with 19 percent response, Instagram ranked sixth with 22 percent of response. The Respondents ranked Quora as the last rank of the social media as they use.

Table – 5 Respondents opinion towards WhatsApp usage

		WhatsApp		Total
		Several Time a Day	Some times a Day	
GENDER	Male	28	17	45
	Female	38	17	55
Total		66	34	100

Source: Primary Data

Table – 5 shows the respondents opinion towards WhatsApp usage, from the analysis it is observed that 66 percent of the respondents used WhatsApp (male 24%) and (female 27%) several time in a day and 34 percent of the respondents (male 17%) and (female 17%) used WhatsApp sometimes a day. It is observed from the study that most of the respondents spent more time on WhatsApp.

Table – 6 Respondents opinion towards You Tube

		YouTube			Total
		Several Time a Day	Some times a Day	Once in a week	
GENDER	Male	22	20	0	42
	Female	33	25	0	58`
Total		55	45	0	100

Source: Primary Data

Table – 6 shows the respondents opinion towards YouTube usage, among the respondents 55 percent of the respondents (male 22%) and (female 33%) used watching YouTube channels several time a day and 45% of the respondents (male 20%) and (female 25%) watching the YouTube channels nearly every day, from the analysis it is noted that the respondents used the You Tube channels more often.

Findings

Among the respondents 37 percent of the respondents were male and 63 percent of them were female, and 12 percent of the respondents belongs to nuclear family and rest of the 88 percent of them were from joint family, and 14 percent of the respondents were married and 86 percent of them were unmarried.

Among the respondents 46 percent of them highly preferred to buy Mi/Redmi brand of Smartphone and 25 percent of the respondents prefer to buy Samsung brand and they give least preference to Apple brand at 2 percent level. There are various reasons behind the preference to buy a Smartphone includes price, size of display, battery level, internal memory, camera pixel etc.

The study found the purpose of using the Smartphone among male and female respondents. Among the respondents 33 percent of the male respondents and 64 percent of the female respondents used their Smart phone for phone calling, so it is concluded that most of the students 97 percent using their Smartphone for phone calling and 69 percent of the respondents used their Smartphone for listening music, among them 20 percent of them are male and 49 percent of them are female respondents, so female respondents use their Smart phone for listening music than male respondents. The study also reveals that 63 percent of the respondents used to watching social media, among them 17 percent of them are male and 46 percent of them are female.

It is found that among the various social Medias the respondents prefer to use WhatsApp social media. Among the respondents 54 percent of them use this social media, and 28 percent of the respondents used YouTube social media, Face Book social media used by 36 percent of the respondents and followed by other social media such as Google+ with 29 percent, Twitter with 19 percent response, among the respondents 22 percent of them use Instagram and 23 percent of them use LinkedIn and followed by Flickr with 29 percent response. The Respondents given least importance to Quora social media.

The study found that 66 percent of the respondents used WhatsApp (male 24%) and (female 27%) several time in a day and 34 percent of the respondents (male 17%) and (female 17%) used WhatsApp sometimes a day. It is observed from the study that most of the respondents spent more time on WhatsApp.

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Conclusion

As the technology is growing the social media has become the routine for each and every person, especially students are seen addicted with these technology every day. With different fields its impact is different on people and social media has increased the quality. Most of the students generally used their smart phone for phone calls, when they used it for social media

networking sites; they use mostly WhatsApp, You Tube and Facebook etc. Positive use of social media can develop the student's academic career, their skills, better living style etc. Social media is a useful tool for students so its use is essential to get information and knowledge. when student going to connect the social media they should keep in mind that basic purpose of use, and they should remember that they are going to share the information or links which are not only for their pleasure and interest but also for all their contacts and friends community, so they should be more careful and utilize with social responsibility. This study investigates the effects of social media on students. Results shows that social media plays important role in social learning. Students mostly use social media for communication with friends.

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